

SEARCHING FOR EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN A STUDY ASSISTANT: AN OPEN SEARCH USE CASE

L. Martin* ,
University of Bamberg, 96047 Bamberg, Germany

Abstract

In recent years we have developed a study planning assistant, for which the extension to a more general study assistant represents an interesting open search use case due to the subjects of search, i.e., (Open) Educational Resources. Considering this use case deepens the understanding of vertical providers' requirements for an Open Search Infrastructure.

STUDY (PLANNING) ASSISTANT

Currently, our study planning assistant supports the process of selecting modules as a student as well as the order in which to attend these. Furthermore, it provides an overview of compulsory and elective modules as well as the students' individual progression within their program. Our planned research aims to extend the capabilities of the current assistant to provide a more general assistant with vertical search features. The possible use case is to provide a (personalized) recommendation system for (open) learning material, which requires the integration of Educational Resources (ERs).

(OPEN) EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

ERs can be defined as "learning, teaching and research materials in any format and medium" [1]. If those resources "reside in the public domain or are [...] released under an open license" [1], they are called Open Educational Resources (OERs). However, OERs often lack findability [2], which is addressed by various OER search projects. Known representatives for vertical search over OER are *OER Commons*¹, targeting various educational levels, and Open Educational Resources Search Index (OERSI)², focused on higher education resources. Apart from vertical searches, projects such as *OERhörnchen*³ execute search queries via Google that are specially configured for OER. Our approach aligns with these projects' common goals of making curated OER more accessible, yet it allows for direct access of educational material not only within the domain of education, but within the context of a study (planning) assistant application by means of an Open Search Infrastructure (OSI).

OPEN SEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

An OSI, as envisioned by the contributors of the OSSYM, provides an interface for accessing a decentralized pool of information sources such as crawls, databases, and indices. A central requirement for implementing the study assistant

using the OSI is an easy integration of ERs or ER providers to the decentralized pool. For this reason, the said integration and management of external information sources in the OSI has to be a benefit for vertical providers and external information source providers as well because most ERs are using laboriously curated indices. Possible ways of incorporating external information sources are integrating the data directly into the OSI, adding the external information sources to the first-hand crawls of the OSI, or leveraging meta searches, i.e., relaying the search to external search providers and post-processing the search engine result pages.

PLANNED RESEARCH

As noted before, ERs are often structured, highly curated, domain specific, and tailored to the users, e.g., regarding previous knowledge. Therefore, we plan to extend the existing study planning assistant with search engine and recommender system features, e.g., matching anonymized user profiles with an ER knowledge graph to identify possible resources of interest for a user's current information need. To establish a ranking of relevant ERs, voting techniques for calculating relative scores [3] are to be applied where previously visited ERs vote for candidates retrieved from the ER knowledge graph. For instance, if computer science students search for ERs with regards to personal preference and previous knowledge, our study assistant is to provide a ranking of ERs that are strongly related to their user profile. This planned research complements our other project investigating the requirements for the interface of an OSI in the context of a company search [4].

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* leon.martin@uni-bamberg.de

¹ *OER commons*. <https://www.oercommons.org> [03.06.2022].

² *OERSI*. <https://oersi.org> [03.06.2022].

³ *OERhörnchen*. <https://oerhoernchen.de> [03.06.2022].